

ON ORGANO-ANTIMONIAL COMPOUNDS. PART

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Some piperazine derivatives of stibinic acid have been synthesised for testing their filaricidal activity.

Various antimony compounds have so far been tried for their antifilaritic properties, but no compound has proved to be the ideal one. They generally have the power of killing adult worms. According to Culbertson and his co-workers (*Amer. J. Trop. Med.*, 1945, 25, 271, 403; *Amer. J. Hygiene*, 1946, 43, 145) neostibosan is the most suitable among the known antimony compounds.

The most active drug, hetrazan (Hewitt *et al.*, *J. Lab. & Clin. Med.*, 1947, 32, 1304, 1314) which is a piperazine derivative, kills the microfilaria very quickly, but it is not very active against adult worms. It was therefore considered desirable to prepare piperazine-antimony compounds to study their antifilaritic properties.

Chloroacetylaminophenylstibinic acid fails to yield the desired antimony compound on condensing with piperazine or N-mono-substituted piperazines. Such compounds have, however, been prepared from the appropriate amine by the Bart-Schmidt reaction as was applied by Morgan and Cook (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 737) for the preparation of quinoline-stibinic acids.

p-Nitro- ω -chloroacetanilide has been reacted with piperazine and mono-substituted piperazine to yield the compounds (I, II; X = NO₂).

These nitro compounds have been successfully reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid in good yields. The amines by the Bart-Schmidt reaction give corresponding stibinic acids which are quite stable. They form sodium and diethylamino salts.

EXPERIMENTAL

Piperazine-1:4-di-p-nitroacetanilide (I, X = NO₂).—Piperazine (4 g., hexahydrate), *p*-nitro- ω -chloroacetanilide (8 g.), sodium acetate (20 g.) and water (100 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as light yellow crystals (6 g.). It melts at 302°. (Found: N, 19.20. C₂₀H₂₂O₆N₆ requires N, 19.0 per cent).

Piperazine-1:4-di-p-aminoacetanilide (I, X = NH₂).—The above nitro compound (4 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and diluted with water (25 c.c.). Zinc dust (6 g.) was gradually added and the reaction completed by heating. The

amine was then liberated by the addition of excess of ice-cold strong caustic soda solution. It can be crystallised from pyridine to a light grey coloured substance, which melts at 255° , and is readily soluble in dilute acids, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 22.1. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_6$ requires N, 21.98 per cent).

Piperazine-1:4-diacetanilide-p-stibinic Acid (I, X = SbO_2H_2).—The above amine (10 g.), dissolved in water (30 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.), was diazotised in cold by the addition of sodium nitrite (4 g.). The diazo solution was slowly added with stirring and simultaneous addition of 6*N* caustic soda solution to an ice-cold solution composed of antimony trichloride (15 g.), 5*N* hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.), glycerol (25 c.c.) and sufficient 6*N* sodium hydroxide to make a clear solution on diluting to one litre. The resulting mixture should be kept alkaline all the time. It was left overnight at room temperature, filtered and the clear solution was acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated antimony compound was purified through stibinic chloride which was subsequently decomposed by cold dilute caustic soda solution, and pure antimony compound was reprecipitated by dilute acetic acid. It is a light brown solid, insoluble in dilute acids. (Found: Sb, 35.7. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_6Sb_2$ requires Sb, 34.84 per cent).

Piperazine-1-carbethoxy-4-p-nitroacetanilide (II; R = CO_2Et , X = NO_2).—Monocarbethoxypiperazine (7.5 g.), *p*-nitro-*o* chloroacetanilide (9 g.), sodium acetate (25 g.) in water (150 c.c.) were refluxed for 3 hours. The pasty mass which formed solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as a yellow crystalline compound, m.p. $134-35^{\circ}$, yield 9 g. (Found N, 17.1. $C_{15}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 16.6 per cent).

Piperazine-1-carbethoxy-4-p-aminoacetanilide (II; R = CO_2Et , X = NH_2).—The above nitro compound was reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid. The base being a pasty mass was extracted with benzene after addition of sufficient cold caustic soda solution to dissolve the zinc hydrate that first formed. After drying the benzene with anhydrous sodium sulphate, the hydrochloride was precipitated by passing dry hydrogen chloride. The hydrochloride was filtered and washed with alcohol. It is a dihydrochloride which can be crystallised from alcohol as colorless needles which melt with forthing at 276° . (Found: N, 15.0; Cl, 19.0. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 14.77; Cl, 18.47 per cent).

Piperazine-1-carbethoxy-4-acetanilide-p-stibinic Acid (II; R = CO_2Et , X = SbO_2H_2).—The above amine was diazotised and subjected to the Bart-Schmidt reaction as has been described before. It is a brown solid and dissolves readily in excess of dilute acids. (Found: Sb, 27.2. $C_{15}H_{22}O_6N_3Sb$ requires Sb, 26.4 per cent).

1:4-Di (phenyl-p-stibinic acid)-piperazine.—1:4-*p*-Diaminodiphenylpiperazine (Morley, *Ber.*, 1880, 12, 1793) was diazotised and subjected to the Bart-Schmidt reaction as before. The antimony compound is insoluble in dilute acids (Found: Sb, 43. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6N_2Sb_2$ requires Sb, 42.06 per cent).

The author is indebted to Prof. M. N. Goswami for his kind interest in this investigation.